

Antispasmodics and Antihistaminics Derived from Hydroxy- and Amino-Chalkones

(Miss) Alaka Banerjee, P. L. Nayak and M. K. Rout

NN-Diethylamino-acetoxy, β -amino-ethoxy, *NN*-diethylamino-acetamido and β -aminoethylamino derivatives have been prepared from hydroxy- and aminochalkones. Some of them have been tested for their antispasmodic and antihistaminic properties and found to possess activities comparable to compounds now used in medicinal practice.

This communication deals with several compounds derived from hydroxy- and amino-chalkones, synthesised on the basis of the hypothesis laid down by Lands *et al.*¹ For the above (i) *NN*-diethylamino-acetoxy derivatives and (ii) β -amino-ethoxy derivatives have been prepared from hydroxy-chalkones, and (iii) *NN*-diethylamino-acetamido derivatives and (iv) β -aminoethylamino derivatives have been prepared from amino-chalkones.

For preparing compounds of type (i), the corresponding hydroxy-chalkones were first condensed with chloroacetyl chloride and the resulting products were made to react with diethylamine under appropriate conditions. Compounds of type (ii) were prepared by condensing hydroxy-chalkones with β -bromoethylamine hydrobromide in dry acetone in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.

Compounds of type (iii) were prepared by condensing the aminochalkones with chloroacetyl chloride and subsequent treatment of the resulting products with diethylamine. Compounds of type (iv) were prepared by condensing aminochalkones with β -bromoethylamine hydrobromide.

The hydroxy chalkones were prepared by using 50% NaOH as the condensing agent.² The aminochalkones were prepared by reduction of nitrochalkones in presence of stannous chloride and HCl³. The nitrochalkones were prepared by using 2*NN*NaOH as the condensing agent.

The antispasmodic and antihistaminic activities of the compounds were evaluated by the extent to which these block the effects of acetylcholine and histamine on strips of Guinea-pig ileum.

Some of the compounds tested possess considerable antispasmodic activity, relaxing 50% of the spasm induced by a standard dose of acetylcholine in a concentration of 2 mg/50 ml.

1. *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1956, 117, 331.
2. Mahal and Venkatraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 817.
3. Dawsey and Gwilt., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1008.

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Among the compounds tested for antihistaminic activity, the most effective was hydrochloride of 2'- β -aminoethoxy-3',4'-benzochalkone. This compound inhibited 50% of the spasm induced by a standard dose of histamine in a concentration of 1.8 mg/50ml. The considerable antihistaminic activity of this compound may be attributed to the presence of a aminoethoxy grouping which appears to be responsible for the activity of benadryl.

EXPERIMENTAL

3'-Chloro-2'-diethylaminoacetoxychalkone—This involved preparation of the intermediate 3'-chloro-2'-chloroacetoxychalkone, which was prepared as follows:

To sodium salt of 2'-hydroxy-3'-chlorochalkone (1.4g.), suspended in dry benzene (12-15ml) in a r.b. flask, chloroacetyl chloride (1.2 g.) was added (the latter may be added in excess). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 1/2 hr. at 70° C. After distilling benzene, the residue was added to a large volume of water and the solid separating was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 110°, yield, 55% (Found: Cl, 21.08. C₁₇H₁₂O₃Cl₂ requires Cl, 21.15%).

The analytical data and m.p. of chloroacetoxy derivatives of the hydroxychalkones are shown in Table-I.

TABLE I

Compounds	R = —O— $\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}$ —CH ₂ —Cl		R = —O— $\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}$ —CH ₂ —NEt ₂		R = —O— $\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}$ —CH ₂ —NEt ₂ .HCl							
	M.P.	Yield	% Chlorine Found.	% Chlorine Reqd.	M.P.	Yield	% Nitrogen Found.	% Nitrogen Reqd.	M.P.	Yield	% Nitrogen Found.	% Nitrogen Reqd.
2-R-C	104°	85%	11.62	11.80	99°	62%	3.98	4.15	110°	80%	3.72	3.75
2'-R-C	98°	80	11.70	11.80	95°	68	4.02	4.15	108°	85	3.70	3.75
4-R-C	95°	83	11.80	11.80	175°	60	4.06	4.15	175°	90	3.73	3.75
3'-Chloro-4'-R-C	107°	73	20.96	21.15	153°	45	3.43	3.78	*	*	*	*
5'-Chloro 2'-R'-C	100°	64	20.65	21.15	110°	55	3.60	3.78	*	*	*	*
3'-Chloro-4'-R-												
4-methoxy -C	102°	53	19.30	19.45	93°	50	3.00	3.49	125°	75	3.00	3.196
5'-Chloro -4-methoxy -2'-R-C	97°	46	19.25	19.45	90°	60	3.48	3.49	76°	65	3.18	3.196
3',4'-Benzo-4-methoxy-2'-R-C	122°	59	9.28	9.31	116°	55	3.23	3.35	140°	78	3.04	3.09
3',4'-Benzo 5'-Nitro -2'-R-C	185°	65	8.90	8.96	156°	45	6.44	6.48	*	*	*	*
3',4'-Benzo-5'-Nitro 4-methoxy -2'-R-C	178°	50	8.29	8.33	198°	48	5.99	6.06	*	*	*	*

C = Chalkone.

*Compounds highly hygroscopic, hence m.p and analytical data could not be determined.

To 3'-chloro-2'-chloroacetoxychalkone (1.68g.), diethylamine (0.73g.) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath at 60-70° for 6 to 8 hr. Diethylamine (each time about 0.5g) was added two or three times in course of heating at the interval of 2 hr. The reaction product was first washed with a very dilute solution of HCl and then with water. It was finally crystallised from benzene, m.p. 80°, yield, 70% (Found: N, 3.72; Cl, 9.37. $C_{21}H_{22}O_3$ NCl requires N 3.77 Cl, 9.54).

The analytical data and m.p. of the diethylaminoacetoxy derivatives of the hydroxychalkone are recorded in Table I.

4-NN-Diethylamino-acetamidochalkone.—This involved the preparation of the intermediate 4-chloro-acetamidochalkone which was obtained from 4-aminochalkone (2.2g) and chloroacetyl chloride (2.5 g.) by a method similar to that used for preparing the chloroacetyl derivative of hydroxy chalkones, m.p. 120°, yield, 49% (Found: N, 4.58; Cl, 11.64. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2$ NCl requires N, 4.67; Cl, 11.83%).

The analytical data and m.p. of the chloroacetamido derivatives of the other aminochalkones prepared are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Compounds	R = $-\text{NH}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_2-\text{Cl}$			R = $-\text{NH}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}.\text{Et}_2$			R = $-\text{NH}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}.\text{Et}_2.\text{HCl}$					
	M.P.	Yield	%Chlorine Found	M.P.	Yield	%Nitrogen Found	M.P.	Yield	%Nitrogen Found			
4-R-C	120°	60%	11.80	11.83	156°	62%	8.15	8.33	184°	78%	7.48	7.31
3-R-C	105°	65	11.83	11.83	142°	53	8.20	8.33	144°	65	7.43	7.51
4'-R-C	80°	69	11.65	11.83	240°	45	8.05	8.33	> 240°	60	7.50	7.51
4'-R-4-methoxy-C	139-40°	80	10.56	10.77	228°	50	7.43	7.65	138°	72	6.91	6.96
1-(4'-R-phenyl)-3-(styryl)-propenone	160°	50	10.83	10.88	210°	45	7.55	7.73	205°	63	6.98	7.03

C = Chalkone.

To 4-chloroacetamido chalkone (1.5g.) in minimum quantity of anhydrous ethanol diethylamine (0.73g.) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath at 60-70° for 6-8 hr. The product, thus formed, was isolated in a manner similar to that used in the case of hydroxychalkone; m.p. 156°, yield, 60%. (Found: C, 74.94; H, 7.08; N, 8.31. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2$ N₂ requires, C, 74.98, H, 7.14, N, 8.33%).

The analytical data and m.p. of the diethylacetamido derivatives of the other aminochalkones are recorded in Table II.

3'-Chloro-2'-aminoethoxychalkone.—To acetone (15 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (4 g.) in a dry conical flask β-bromoethylamine hydrobromide (4.1 g.) was added and the contents were thoroughly mixed. To this the sodium salt of 3'-chloro-2'-hydroxychalkone (2.8g) was added with shaking. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 10 hr. Acetone was distilled and water was added to the residue after cooling. It was kept overnight when the residue solidified. After filtration the residue was again

washed with water two or three times and then crystallised from ethanol m.p. 112°, yield 60% (Found: C 67.59; H 5.23; N 4.53; Cl 11.64. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$ NCl requires C, 67.66 H, 5.34; N, 4.64; Cl, 11.75%). The analytical data and the m.p. of the β -aminoethoxy derivatives of other hydroxy chalkones are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Compound	R = —O—CH ₂ —CH ₂ —NH ₂		R = —O—CH ₂ —CH ₂ —NH ₂ . HCl		R = —O—CH ₂ —CH ₂ —NH ₂ . HCl		R = —O—CH ₂ —CH ₂ —NH ₂ . HCl	
	M.P.	Yield	% Nitrogen Found	% Nitrogen Req'd.	M.P.	Yield	% Nitrogen Found	% Nitrogen Req'd.
2-R-C	95°	60%	5.19	5.24	106°	69%	4.60	4.61
2'-R-C	92°	52	5.15	5.24	110°	80	4.53	4.61
4-R-C	83°	45	5.17	5.24	95°	85	4.57	4.61
5'-Chloro-2'-R-C	135°	68	4.52	4.64	99°	65	4.11	4.13
5'-Chloro-4-methoxy 2'-R-C	111°	80	4.15	4.20	123°	70	3.75	3.78
3'4'-Benzo-4-methoxy 2'-R-C	116°	60	3.95	4.02	135°	62	3.62	3.65
2'3'-Benzo-4-methoxy 6'-R-C	81°	56	3.98	4.02	132°	59	3.60	3.65
3'-4'-Benzo-2'-R-C	112°	69	4.39	4.41	116°	68	3.90	3.96
3'-Chloro-2'-R-C	112°	60	4.53	4.64	136°	69	4.09	4.13

C = Chalkone

Hydrobromide of 4-Amino-ethylaminochalkone.—To 4-aminochalkone (2.2g.) β -bromoethylamine hydrobromide (2.1g) in ethanol (10-15ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. The solid separating on cooling was filtered and dried in a desiccator. m.p. 163°, yield, 60%. (Found: C, 58.46; H, 5.65; N, 7.97; Br, 22.80. $C_{17}H_{19}ON_2Br$ requires C, 58.79; H, 5.51; N, 8.06; Br, 23.01).

The analytical data and the m.p. of the other compounds are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Compounds	R = —NH—CH ₂ —CH ₂ —NH ₂ —HBr.			
	M.P.	Yield	% Nitrogen	
			Found	Req'd.
4-R-C	163°	65%	8.03	8.07
4'-R-C	113°	45	7.96	8.07
3-R-C	230°	64	7.98	8.07
4-methoxy				
4'-R-C	209°	59	7.39	7.43

C = Chalkone

The hydrochlorides of *NN*-diethylamino-acetoxy and β -amino-ethoxy derivatives of the hydroxychalkones and *NN*-diethylamino-acetamido derivatives of the amino-chalkones were prepared by dissolving the above compounds in minimum amount of pure and dry ether or acetone and passing pure and dry HCl gas through the solution for a few minutes when the hydrochlorides separated. The solvent was decanted and the product dried in a desiccator.

The analytical data and the m.p. of the corresponding hydrochlorides are recorded in the relative tables.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE,
CUTTACK-3.

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